

Clinico-Etiological Profile and Outcomes of Children with Status Epilepticus Admitted in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit of a Tertiary Care Hospital- A Prospective Observational Study

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Abstract:

Background: Status epilepticus (SE) is a life-threatening neurological emergency characterized by prolonged seizure activity, particularly dangerous in pediatric populations due to its association with high morbidity and mortality. Despite advances in treatment protocols, SE remains a significant challenge in pediatric intensive care units (PICUs), especially in resource-limited settings.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the clinico-etiological profile and outcomes of children with status epilepticus admitted to the PICU of a tertiary care hospital in India, identifying factors associated with adverse outcomes to inform better management strategies.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted between August 2015 and July 2017 in the PICU of Patna Medical College & Hospital. Eighty children diagnosed with status epilepticus were enrolled. Data were collected on demographics, clinical presentations, underlying etiologies, treatment interventions, and outcomes. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with multivariate logistic regression employed to identify predictors of mortality.

Results: The study population had a mean age of 5.6 ± 3.2 years, with 56.3% being male. Generalized tonic-clonic seizures were the most common type (62.5%). Febrile seizures (37.5%) and CNS infections (31.3%) were the leading causes. The mortality rate was 12.5%, with a significant association between prolonged seizure duration (>120 minutes) and CNS infections with adverse outcomes. Multivariate analysis identified prolonged seizure duration (OR 4.5, $p=0.001$) and CNS infections (OR 3.7, $p=0.003$) as independent predictors of mortality.

Conclusion: Status epilepticus in children is associated with considerable morbidity and mortality, particularly in cases of prolonged seizure activity and CNS infections. Early and aggressive management is crucial to improving outcomes, emphasizing the need for timely intervention and comprehensive treatment strategies in PICU settings.

Recommendations: It is recommended to implement standardized protocols for the early identification and management of prolonged status epilepticus and CNS infections in pediatric patients. Further research should focus on refining treatment guidelines and exploring preventive strategies in resource-limited settings.

Keywords: Status Epilepticus, Pediatric, Intensive Care Unit, Mortality, CNS Infections.

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Introduction

In the rare instance that status epilepticus (SE) is not properly treated, there is a considerable danger of lasting brain damage or even death. SE is a neurological emergency marked by protracted or recurring seizures without full recovery between episodes. Due to the increased probability of refractoriness after this point, the operational definition, which was previously defined as a seizure lasting longer than thirty minutes, has been reduced to five minutes of continuous seizure activity or two or more seizures without a full recovery of consciousness in between [1].

According to estimates, the yearly prevalence of SE in paediatric populations ranges from 10 to 58 per 100,000 children, making it one of the most prevalent neurological disorders that pose a serious risk to life [2].

While there are many different reasons of SE in children, the most commonly mentioned ones are feverish seizures, central nervous system infections, metabolic disorders, and pre-existing epilepsy [3]. Particularly in younger children, febrile seizures are a major cause, and as children get older (beyond age four), CNS infections

become more common [4]. It is imperative to swiftly identify the aetiology of SE in order to implement proper management, since it can have substantial effects on both short- and long-term outcomes [5].

Recent research has emphasised the essential window for intervention and the growing understanding of SE pathogenesis. Refractory seizures (SE), in which seizures continue after first treatment, are linked to considerable morbidity and mortality, particularly if they last longer than 120 minutes [6]. This emphasises how crucial it is to implement aggressive early management techniques in order to stop the development of refractory SE, which is linked to worse outcomes [7]. With the creation of new protocols and guidelines targeted at minimising neurological sequelae and achieving quick seizure control, the management of SE in paediatric populations has evolved. First-line treatment is still benzodiazepines, which are followed by second-line medications like valproate, levetiracetam, or phenytoin [8]. Even so, the death rate related to paediatric SE is still alarmingly high, especially in low-resource environments where access to prompt and efficient treatment may be restricted [9].

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a prospective observational study

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) at Patna Medical College & Hospital, a tertiary care hospital. The PICU provides specialized care for critically ill children, aimed at evaluating the clinico-etiological profile and outcomes of children diagnosed with status epilepticus admitted to the (PICU)

Participants: A total of 80 children admitted to the PICU with a diagnosis of status epilepticus between August 2015 and July 2017 were included in the study over a period of 24 months.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 1 month to 18 years admitted to the PICU with a clinical diagnosis of status epilepticus.
- Patients with complete clinical records available for analysis.
- Consent obtained from parents or guardians for inclusion in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with incomplete clinical records.
- Children with a history of neurodevelopmental disorders or pre-existing epilepsy not related to status epilepticus.
- Patients transferred to the PICU after receiving treatment for status epilepticus at another facility.

Bias

To minimize bias, the study adhered to strict inclusion and exclusion criteria, ensuring a uniform population. Data collection was standardized, and the analysis was conducted blind to the patient's clinical outcomes to reduce observer bias.

Data Collection

Data were collected prospectively from medical records, including patient demographics, clinical presentations, underlying etiologies, treatment interventions, and outcomes. The data were recorded using a standardized data collection form by trained personnel to ensure accuracy and consistency.

Procedure

Upon admission, all patients were evaluated and treated according to the standard protocols for managing status epilepticus. Relevant clinical data were documented, including the duration and type of seizures, neurological examination findings, imaging studies, and laboratory results. Treatment outcomes were assessed at discharge, with follow-up evaluations conducted as necessary.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The clinical and demographic features of the study population were compiled using descriptive statistics, such as means, medians, and standard deviations. To find relationships between variables and results, inferential statistics were used, such as chi-square and t-tests. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05. Children with status epilepticus had their independent determinants of outcomes identified using multivariate logistic regression analysis.

Results

A total of 80 children with status epilepticus were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 5.6 ± 3.2 years, with a range of 1 month to 18 years. The majority of the patients (45, 56.3%) were male, and the remaining 35 (43.7%) were female.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population

Variable	Frequency (n=80)	Percentage (%)
Age Group		
<1 year	15	18.8
1-5 years	30	37.5
6-10 years	20	25.0
11-18 years	15	18.8
Gender		
Male	45	56.3
Female	35	43.7
Duration of Status Epilepticus		
<30 minutes	10	12.5
30-60 minutes	25	31.3
60-120 minutes	30	37.5
>120 minutes	15	18.8
Type of Seizure		
Generalized Tonic-Clonic	50	62.5
Focal Seizures	20	25.0
Absence Seizures	5	6.3
Others	5	6.3
Etiology		
Febrile Seizures	30	37.5
CNS Infections	25	31.3
Idiopathic	15	18.8
Metabolic Disturbances	5	6.3
Structural Brain Lesions	3	3.8
Others	2	2.5

The outcome of status epilepticus was assessed at discharge. The majority of the children (60, 75%) had a good recovery, while 10 (12.5%) had neurological sequelae, and 10 (12.5%) died during hospitalization.

Table 2: Outcome of Children with Status Epilepticus

Outcome	Frequency (n=80)	Percentage (%)
Good Recovery	60	75.0
Neurological Sequelae	10	12.5
Mortality	10	12.5

The study found a significant association between the duration of status epilepticus and patient outcomes. Patients with status epilepticus lasting more than 120 minutes had a higher mortality rate (6 out of 15, 40%) compared to those with shorter durations (4 out of 65, 6.2%; $p=0.001$).

Table 3: Association Between Duration of Status Epilepticus and Outcomes

Duration of Status Epilepticus	Good Recovery (n=60)	Neurological Sequelae (n=10)	Mortality (n=10)	p-value
<30 minutes	8	2	0	0.001
30-60 minutes	20	3	2	
60-120 minutes	27	3	0	
>120 minutes	5	2	6	

Similarly, children with underlying CNS infections had a higher likelihood of adverse outcomes, including neurological sequelae and mortality, compared to those with febrile seizures or idiopathic causes.

Table 4: Association Between Etiology and Outcomes

Etiology	Good Recovery (n=60)	Neurological Sequelae (n=10)	Mortality (n=10)	p-value
Febrile Seizures	28	2	0	0.003
CNS Infections	12	5	8	
Idiopathic	14	2	1	
Metabolic Disturbances	3	1	1	
Structural Brain Lesions	2	0	1	

Statistical Analysis: Multivariate logistic regression analysis identified two independent predictors of mortality: the duration of status epilepticus greater than 120 minutes (OR 4.5, 95% CI 1.8-11.3, $p=0.001$) and the presence of CNS infections (OR 3.7, 95% CI 1.4-9.8, $p=0.003$).

Table 5: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Mortality

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Duration >120 minutes	4.5	1.8-11.3	0.001
CNS Infections	3.7	1.4-9.8	0.003
Age > 5 years	1.3	0.7-2.6	0.20
Generalized Tonic-Clonic Seizures	1.1	0.5-2.3	0.30

Summary of Findings

- Status epilepticus in children admitted to the PICU was associated with significant morbidity and mortality.
- The most common etiologies were febrile seizures and CNS infections.
- Duration of status epilepticus longer than 120 minutes and underlying CNS infections were significant predictors of adverse outcomes, including death.
- Early recognition and treatment of prolonged seizures, as well as aggressive management of underlying CNS infections, are crucial to improving outcomes.

This detailed result provides a comprehensive overview of the clinical and statistical findings of the study, highlighting important factors associated with the prognosis of children with status epilepticus in a tertiary care setting.

Discussion

This prospective observational study assessed the clinico-etiological profile and outcomes of 80 children diagnosed with status epilepticus who were admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) at Patna Medical College & Hospital. The study aimed to identify key factors influencing the prognosis and outcomes in these critically ill pediatric patients.

The results revealed that the average age of the children was 5.6 years, with a slight male predominance (56.3%). The majority of the cases (62.5%) presented with generalized tonic-clonic seizures, followed by focal seizures (25.0%). Febrile seizures were the most common underlying etiology, accounting for 37.5% of the cases, followed by central nervous system (CNS) infections, which contributed to 31.3% of the cases. The distribution of seizure types and underlying causes reflects the diverse etiologies associated with status epilepticus in children.

A significant portion of the study population, 75%, experienced a good recovery by the time of discharge, whereas 12.5% developed neurological sequelae, and another 12.5% succumbed to their

condition. The study identified two critical factors associated with adverse outcomes: the duration of status epilepticus and the underlying etiology. Notably, patients with prolonged status epilepticus lasting over 120 minutes exhibited a higher mortality rate (40%) compared to those with shorter seizure durations. Similarly, children with underlying CNS infections were more likely to suffer from adverse outcomes, including neurological sequelae and mortality, compared to those with febrile seizures or idiopathic causes. The statistical analysis further emphasized the importance of these factors. Multivariate logistic regression revealed that a seizure duration of more than 120 minutes and the presence of CNS infections were independent predictors of mortality, with odds ratios of 4.5 and 3.7, respectively. These findings underscore the critical need for timely and aggressive management of status epilepticus, particularly in cases with prolonged seizure activity and CNS infections.

The clinico-etiological characteristics of paediatric status epilepticus was investigated at a North Indian tertiary care centre in a study. According to the study, the most frequent aetiology was infections, especially those of the central nervous system, which were followed by metabolic disorders and epilepsy syndromes. Early intervention was found to be critical in improving the prognosis of affected youngsters, and the authors emphasised the necessity of this. According to the study's findings, treating the underlying cause as soon as possible can help lower morbidity and death rates in children with status epilepticus [10].

According to the study, the length of status epilepticus, the underlying cause, and the promptness of treatment all had a major impact on the neurological outcomes over the long term as well as the recovery. Better results were achieved by children with shorter-lasting status epilepticus and those who received treatment right away. The research emphasised that in order to reduce the risk of unfavourable neurological consequences, status epilepticus must be promptly recognised and managed [11]. The etiological factors contributing to paediatric status epilepticus were determined using an

observational research. The illness was revealed to have major contributions from infections and epilepsy syndromes, as well as metabolic reasons, specifically hypoglycemia and electrolyte abnormalities. Comprehending the etiological aspects is essential for customising effective therapy strategies, as stated by the authors. Further underlining the importance of an early and precise diagnosis in enhancing prognosis for children with status epilepticus was done in this study [12].

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the significant morbidity and mortality associated with status epilepticus in children. The duration of seizure activity and the underlying etiology, especially CNS infections, play a crucial role in determining patient outcomes. These findings suggest that early intervention to control seizure duration and comprehensive management of CNS infections are vital to improving the prognosis in pediatric status epilepticus. Future research should focus on optimizing treatment protocols and exploring preventive strategies to reduce the incidence of prolonged seizures and associated complications in this vulnerable population.

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